

Biochemical Effects of Nano-Silicon Dioxide (SiO₂) on Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) plants: with SEM-EDX Analysis

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Abstract

Silicon is among the most abundant elements on earth after oxygen. Studies have shown that silicon nanoparticles contribute to plant growth and development. Nano particles [NP] are important due to their unique properties associated with high surface-to-volume ratio, and they have many application areas including agricultural industry, pharmacy, and medicine. In this study, different sizes and concentrations of SiO₂NP were applied to sunflower plants. Chlorophyll determination was made in leaf tissue, antioxidant enzyme activities, malondialdehyde (MDA), Si assay, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analyzes were made in root and leaf tissues of sunflower treated with SiO₂NP in different sizes and concentrations. According to the data we have obtained, it has been shown that silicon nanoparticles reduce the damage caused by abiotic stress together with the active defense system of plants. However, NPs are thought to trigger the formation of reactive oxygen species due to their increased antioxidant enzyme activities and cause anatomical changes, especially on the leaf surface and root tissue, as shown by SEM analysis

Keywords: *Helianthus annuus L., Nano-Silicon Dioxide, Antioxidant Enzymes, SEM, EDX*

Introduction

Nanotechnology is defined as developing more advanced materials, tools and systems by processing matter at an atomic or molecular level. Materials smaller than 100 nm are classified as nanoparticles/nanomaterials. Nano technological materials exhibit very different properties than micrometric or larger molecules as a result of their size (Farhangi-Abriz and Torabian 2018). Nanotechnology has created a new field of application in the biotechnology and agriculture sector. Although studies have been performed on the harmful effects of nanoparticles in plant systems, few studies have been conducted on plant growth and development (Milewska et al. 2016). Nanotechnology has the potential to make a breakthrough in the agriculture and food industry with new approaches such as improving the ability of plants to take up nutrients. Effect of NPs on plant varieties; it depends on the content, concentration, size and important physicochemical properties of NPs. NPs can enter the cell with various ways. The main of these ways are; binding to proteins is to form new pores with endocytosis via aquaporin and to organic chemicals in the environment. NPs that enter the cell can be transported apoplasmic or simplistically from one cell to another via plasmodesma. The surface properties of NPs gain importance during this transport. The effects of supportive and inhibitory effects of NPs on plant growth are investigated. The uptake of nanoparticles by plants is affected by various factors related to the nature of NP, it is also affected by plant physiology and the interaction of NPs with the environment. It is stated that the properties of NP will greatly affect the movement and absorption of plants. The NP size appears to be one of the main boundaries of penetration into plant tissues, and there are some reports about the maximum dimensions that plants allow particles between 40 and 50 nm to move and accumulate inside the cells (Taylor et al. 1998, Sabo-Atwood et al.2012). Plant species may differ in their physiology, and such differences result in changes related to the uptake of NPs. The roots are specialized in the absorption of nutrients and water, whereas the leaves are developed for gas exchange, and a cuticle appears that prevents the penetration of substances. The effects of the supporting and preventive effects of nanoparticles on plant growth are being investigated. The defense system against reactive oxygen species [ROS] includes enzymatic scavengers such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), peroxidases (POX) and catalase (CAT) or ascorbate, glutathione, alpha-tocopherol (Noctor and Foyer 1998). The interactions of NPs with plants cause many morphological and physiological changes. Researchers have reported that NPs have both positive and negative effects on plant growth and

development. The effects of NPs vary from plant to plant (Rastogi et al. 2017) and silicon (Si) is an essential element for plant growth and development. Plants take up silicon as a neutralized orthosilicic acid monomer (H_4SiO_4), which is the monomeric form that can cross the root plasma membrane at physiological pH. It has been reported that silicon plays a role in reducing the harmful effects of biotic and abiotic stress in different plants. These positive effects may be related to the high accumulation of silicon on the tissue surface, thus reducing the absorption of soil pollutants such as heavy metals due to increased antioxidant activities of plants. It has been reported that Si application increases the salt tolerance by concentrating sodium ions in the apoplast, and significantly increases the growth of many plants by increasing photosynthetic parameters, such as chlorophyll content and leaf area in plants exposed to salt (Rastogi et al. 2017, Farhangi-Abriz and Torabian 2018). It is stated that the silicon content in plants varies between 0.1 and 10% and this depends on different silicon uptake mechanisms. It has been reported that NPs can offer green and environmentally friendly solutions as an alternative to chemical fertilizers, without harming the nature, therefore, Si-NPs can be concrete solutions to many agricultural problems related to weeds, pathogenicity, drought, crop yield and productivity. The response of plants to NPs depends on various factors such as NP size, shape, application method, chemical and physical properties (Rastogi et al. 2017). In recent studies, it has been reported that Si-NPs can interact directly with plants and affect the morphology and physiology of plants, including adding structural colors to plants, contributing to enhancing plant growth and yield. However, some studies have also shown that Si-NPs have negative effects on plants (Siddiqui et al. 2014). The unique physicochemical properties of nanoscale Si-NPs have beneficial applications in diverse industries, including promising applications in agriculture. It has been noted that the application of Si-NPs in agriculture can assist in the development of high-efficiency improved varieties, leading to global food security (Rastogi et al. 2019). In the present study, the physiological and biochemical effects of nano- SiO_2 application in different sizes and concentrations on sunflower plants, which have economic importance in terms of agriculture, were investigated. SOD, CAT and APX enzyme activities, MDA content and Si quantification were performed in root and leaf tissues. At the same time, the anatomical effects of nano- SiO_2 on leaf and root tissues were investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis.

Material and Methods

Sunflower seeds (*Helianthus annuus L.* LG-5448) used as test material in this study were obtained from Trakya Agricultural Research Institute. Synthesis and Structural Characterization of SiO_2 NPs: Within the scope of the study, 2 different particle sizes of approximately 50 nm and 100 nm SiO_2 structure were synthesized. In these syntheses, tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) was used as the starting material and syntheses were carried out using the surfactant-free sol-gel method. 50 mL of TEOS was taken under nitrogen atmosphere in a 250 mL nitrogen (schlenk) tube and mixed with the active reactant mixture. A mixture of 250 mL of water, 100 mL of acetic acid and 60 mL of ethanol was used as the active reactant mixture. TEOS solution added to the reaction mixture for 2 hours at a stirring speed of 1000 rpm. The resulting colloidal solution centrifuged and washed several times with ethanol. The resulting product was dried at 60 °C for 1 night and calcined for 1 hour at 600 °C. As a result, particles of 50 and 100 nm were obtained. The prepared SiO_2 NPs were first analyzed using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer (FTIR). The infrared spectrum of SiO_2 NPs recorded with Perkin Elmer Spectrum Two FTIR spectrometer in the range of 400-4000 cm^{-1} . The morphology of the root and leaf after treated with SiO_2 NPs was analyzed by SEM (LEO EVO-40xVP). The acceleration voltage was determined as 20 kV and the working distance for analysis as 3 mm, and the chemical composition of SiO_2 NPs was analyzed by EDX; Rönteck Xflash detector analyzer connected to the LEO EVO-40xVP scanning electron microscope was used. Hoagland culture solution was used as the main culture solution in this study. The composition of the Hoagland culture solution was prepared according to Hoagland and Arnon (1950). In this study, the physiological and biochemical effects of nano- SiO_2 application in different sizes and concentrations on sunflower plants. 50 and 100 nm sized SiO_2 NPs were prepared in Hoagland culture solution with concentrations of 20 mg/L and 50 mg/L. All studies covering the germination and growing period were carried out under controlled conditions in the plant growth chamber. In both stages, the temperature in the plant growth chamber was adjusted to 24 ± 1 °C day and night and the relative humidity to $65 \pm 5\%$, and the conditions remained constant

during the experiment. In the growth cycle, the plants were left in a 15 hour light and 9 hour dark period. The lighting intensity in the plant growth room is 12,000 lux on the plant leaf surface. 90% of the illumination intensity was provided by fluorescent lamps and 10% by incandescent lamps. In the study, superoxide dismutase (SOD) (Beyer and Fridowich 1987), catalase (CAT) (Chandlee and Scandalios 1984), ascorbate peroxidase enzyme activities (APX) (Miyake and Asada 1992), malondialdehyde (MDA) level (Madhava and Stresty 2000), chlorophyll amounts (Lichtentaler 1987), Si quantitation (Lukacova et al. 2013), SEM (Scanning Electron Microscope) and EDX spectra analyzes were performed. Elemental maps of Na, Mg, K, Ca, C, O, Si and P and EDX spectra were taken at a magnification of 150X. SEM and EDX spectra analyze were carried out before and after the application of SiO₂NP analyzes on samples that were applied 50 and 100 nm SiO₂. Studies were done in 3 replicates and results were given as mean±SE. The variance analysis of the data obtained as a result of the analysis was determined according to the Friedman and Kruskal-Wallis test using the SPSS 22.0 program.

Results

SEM and EDX analyze of leaf and root structures were analyzed as a result of the applications of 20-50 mg/mL concentrations of ~ 100 nm and ~ 50 nm Nano-SiO₂ particles. The amount of silicon in the leaf tissue of the sunflower plant to which control and Nano-SiO₂ was applied in different concentrations are given in Table 1. SOD, CAT, APX, enzyme activities and MDA level were assayed in the leaves of the sunflowers after treated with Nano-SiO₂ (Table 2-6). As seen in Table 1, Si levels in the control root tissue of *Helianthus annuus L.* increased compared to the control group, depending on both the treatments groups and time. The highest Si level was found as 15.73±0.13 ppm on the 4th day in the 100-50 (nm-mg/L) group in the root tissue. Si levels increased approximately 2-3 times in the root tissue at 4th day compared to the 1st day. It was determined that the difference between all groups, the amount of Si in root tissue depending on time was found to be significant (p≤0.05).

Table 1. Silicon levels in *Helianthus annuus L.* plant leaf and root tissue treated with Nano-SiO₂.

		Control	50-20 [nm-mg/L]	50-50 [nm-mg/L]	100-20 [nm-mg/L]	100-50 [nm-mg/L]
1st day	Root	1.47±0.09 ^{a#}	2.59±0.14 ^{b#}	3.48±0.16 ^{c#}	4.81±0.11 ^{d#}	6.76±0.14 ^{e#}
	Leaf	4.57±0.18 ^{a1}	4.05±0.08 ^{a1}	5.93±0.05 ^{b1}	6.61±0.16 ^{c1}	8.38±0.31 ^{d1}
4th day	Root	1.42±0.13 ^{a#}	6.10±0.13 ^{b*}	8.39±0.16 ^{c*}	13.21±0.28 ^{d*}	15.73±0.13 ^{e*}
	Leaf	4.34±0.08 ^{a1}	4.06±0.16 ^{a1}	7.69±0.19 ^{b1}	9.62±0.07 ^{c2}	15.63±0.14 ^{d2}

Values are given as the mean± SE. The differences between the results shown with different letters in each row and different numbers and symbols in columns are statistically significant [p <0.05].

Table 2. SOD enzyme activities in the root and leaf tissue of *Helianthus annuus L.* treated with Nano-SiO₂.

		Control	50-20 [nm-mg/L]	50-50 [nm-mg/L]	100-20 [nm-mg/L]	100-50 [nm-mg/L]
1st day	Root	81.41±0.34 ^{a#}	12.86±0.33 ^{b#}	15.00±0.1b ^{c#}	31.12±0.63 ^{d#}	65.87±1.22 ^{e#}
	Leaf	74.96±1.01 ^{a1}	15.85±0.50 ^{b1}	45.67±0.19 ^{c1}	51.89±0.62 ^{d1}	78.09±0.10 ^{e1}
4th day	Root	83.00±0.57 ^{a#}	18.79±0.06 ^{b*}	25.74±0.66 ^{c*}	59.03±0.34 ^{d*}	104.25±0.43 ^{e*}
	Leaf	82.09±0.16 ^{a1}	10.67±0.18 ^{b2}	104.87±0.08 ^{c2}	59.66±1.33 ^{d2}	149.94±0.86 ^{e2}

Values are given as the mean± SE. The differences between the results shown with different letters in each row and different numbers and symbols in columns are statistically significant [p <0.05].

In the groups treated with 50-20 (nm-mg.L⁻¹) SiO₂, SOD enzyme activities decreased by 6.3 times at the 1st day and by 4.4 times at the 4th day compared to the control group (p≤0.05). The lowest SOD activity in root tissue was detected as 12.86±0.33 U.mg protein⁻¹ at the 24 th hour of 50-20 (nm-mg.L⁻¹) SiO₂ application. SOD activities increased in 50-50, 100-20, 100-50 (nm-mg.L⁻¹) groups compared to 50-20 (nm-mg.L⁻¹) SiO₂ application. Except for the control group, the differences between the SOD enzyme activities in root tissues depending on the days in all treatment groups were found to be significant

($p \leq 0.059$). SOD activity in the control group of *Helianthus annuus L.* plant leaf tissue at 1st and 4th days, respectively; It was detected as 74.96 ± 1.01 and 82.09 ± 0.16 U.mg protein⁻¹. SOD enzyme activities in the groups treated with 50-20 (nm-mg.L⁻¹) SiO₂ decreased by a factor of 4.7 at the 1st day and 7.6 at the 4th day compared to the control group ($p \leq 0.05$). CAT enzyme activity in sun flower plant control root tissue was determined as 11.95 ± 0.02 , 11.61 ± 0.40 ($\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{min}^{-1} \cdot \text{gFW}^{-1}$) at 1st and 4th days, respectively (Table 3). CAT activities increased depending on the days in all treatment groups compared to the control. The highest CAT activity was 33.90 ± 0.43 ($\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{min}^{-1} \cdot \text{gFW}^{-1}$) with an approximately 3-fold increase at the 4th day in the 100-20 (nm-mg.L⁻¹) SiO₂ treated group ($p \leq 0.05$). CAT activities in 50-50 and 100-20 (nm-mg.L⁻¹) SiO₂ applications compared to the 50-20 (nm-mg.L⁻¹) SiO₂ group, increased approximately 1.3-1.7 times depending on the days. The highest CAT activity was found to be 38.66 ± 0.30 ($\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{min}^{-1} \cdot \text{gFW}^{-1}$) with an approximately 3-fold increase at the 4th day in the 100-20 (nm-mg/L) SiO₂ treated group ($p \leq 0.05$). The differences between the results found in the different size/concentration application group in leaf tissue compared to the control were found to be statistically significant [$p \leq 0.05$].

Table 3. CAT enzyme activities in the root and leaf tissue of *Helianthus annuus L.* treated with Nano-SiO₂

		Control	50-20 [nm-mg/L]	50-50 [nm-mg/L]	100-20 [nm-mg/L]	100-50 [nm-mg/L]
1st day	Root	$11.95 \pm 0.02^{a\#}$	$17.74 \pm 0.15^{b\#}$	$13.66 \pm 0.69^{a\#}$	$24.43 \pm 0.39^{c\#}$	$15.04 \pm 0.24^{a\#}$
	Leaf	15.76 ± 0.70^{a1}	16.86 ± 0.61^{a1}	22.01 ± 0.69^{b1}	25.71 ± 0.30^{b1}	13.54 ± 0.43^{c1}
4th day	Root	$11.61 \pm 0.40^{a\#}$	$22.62 \pm 0.70^{b\#}$	$28.47 \pm 0.39^{c\#}$	$33.90 \pm 0.43^{d\#}$	$21.13 \pm 0.58^{b\#}$
	Leaf	11.21 ± 0.32^{a2}	21.96 ± 0.49^{b2}	34.72 ± 0.16^{c2}	38.66 ± 0.30^{d2}	20.98 ± 0.13^{b2}

Values are given as the mean \pm SE. The differences between the results shown with different letters in each row and different numbers and symbols in columns are statistically significant [$p < 0.05$].

APX enzyme activity in the control root tissue of *Helianthus annuus L.* plant was determined as 0.31 ± 0.01 and 0.32 ± 0.01 $\mu\text{M} \cdot \text{min}^{-1} \cdot \text{mg protein}^{-1}$ at 1st and 4th days, respectively (Table 4). APX activities increased depending on the days in all treatment groups (except the 1st day 100-50 nm-mg.L⁻¹) compared to the control. The highest APX activity was determined as 0.52 ± 0.01 $\mu\text{M} \cdot \text{min}^{-1} \cdot \text{mg protein}^{-1}$ at the 4th day 50-50 (nm-mg.L⁻¹) SiO₂ treated group. It was found that the difference between APX enzyme activity in all treatment groups depending on the size/concentration in the root tissue compared to the control (except 50-50 nm-mg.L⁻¹ at 1st and 4th day) was insignificant ($p \geq 0.05$). It was determined that the difference between APX enzyme activities depending on time at all concentrations of nano-Si application (except 50-20 nm-mg.L⁻¹ at 1st day) in leaf tissue compared to the control ($p \leq 0.05$).

Table 4. APX enzyme activities in the root and leaf tissue of *Helianthus annuus L.* treated with Nano-SiO₂

		Control	50-20 [nm-mg/L]	50-50 [nm-mg/L]	100-20 [nm-mg/L]	100-50 [nm-mg/L]
1st day	Root	$0.31 \pm 0.01^{a\#}$	$0.36 \pm 0.02^{a\#}$	$0.43 \pm 0.01^{b\#}$	$0.34 \pm 0.01^{a\#}$	$0.30 \pm 0.01^{a\#}$
	Leaf	0.28 ± 0.01^{a1}	0.32 ± 0.01^{a1}	0.45 ± 0.01^{b1}	0.38 ± 0.01^{c1}	0.37 ± 0.02^{c1}
4th day	Root	$0.32 \pm 0.01^{a\#}$	$0.42 \pm 0.01^{b\#}$	$0.52 \pm 0.01^{c\#}$	$0.44 \pm 0.01^{b\#}$	$0.43 \pm 0.01^{b\#}$
	Leaf	0.30 ± 0.01^{a1}	0.35 ± 0.01^{b1}	0.48 ± 0.01^{c1}	0.38 ± 0.01^{d1}	0.44 ± 0.01^{e1}

Values are given as the mean \pm SE. The differences between the results shown with different letters in each row and different numbers and symbols in columns are statistically significant [$p < 0.05$].

MDA levels in the root and leaf tissue of sunflower plants treated with control and different concentrations of Nano-SiO₂ are given in Table 5. In the 50-20 (nm-mg.L⁻¹) SiO₂ group, MDA levels decreased at 1st and 4th days compared to the control. MDA levels in 50-50, 100-20 and 100-50 (nm-mg.L⁻¹) SiO₂ groups increased compared to the control (50-50 nm-mg.L⁻¹ 1st day except). The highest MDA level in leaf tissue was detected as 5.63 ± 0.04 $\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{gFW}^{-1}$ at 4th day in the 100-50 (nm-mg.L⁻¹) group. The difference between the MDA levels are significant in all treatment groups at the 1st day of Nano-SiO₂ application (except the 100-20 and 100-50 (nm-mg.L⁻¹) and 4th day, depending on the control, in leaf tissue ($p \leq 0.05$).

Table 5. MDA levels in the root and leaf tissue of *Helianthus annuus L.* treated with Nano-SiO₂

		Control	50-20 [nm-mg/L]	50-50 [nm-mg/L]	100-20 [nm-mg/L]	100-50 [nm-mg/L]
1st day	Root	2.97±0.07 ^{a#}	2.06±0.02 ^{b#}	2.37±0.08 ^{b#}	3.92±0.05 ^{c#}	3.09±0.18 ^{a#}
	Leaf	4.60±0.04 ^{a1}	2.18±0.02 ^{b1}	2.21±0.07 ^{b1}	4.08±0.02 ^{a1}	4.97±0.02 ^{a1}
4th day	Root	2.48±0.04 ^{a#}	1.96±0.02 ^{d#}	3.39±0.03 ^{c#}	3.52±0.18 ^{c#}	5.23±0.25 ^{b*}
	Leaf	4.12±0.05 ^{a1}	2.83±0.04 ^{c2}	2.82±0.04 ^{c1}	3.63±0.04 ^{d1}	5.63±0.04 ^{b1}

Values are given as the mean± SE. The differences between the results shown with different letters in each row and different numbers and symbols in columns are statistically significant [p <0.05].

Figure 1 and 6 show the control group of the leaf and root EDX and SEM spectra. In EDX and SEM spectra of leaves and root structures applied SiO₂ in different sizes and concentrations are shown in Figure 2-5 and 7-10. In these spectra, it was determined that the Si element signal increased due to the increase in the amount of Nano-SiO₂ and the increase in size, and Si clusters in certain regions on the surface. When leaf surfaces with this distribution are evaluated by SEM analysis, it is seen that they show multicellular long trichomes in the partial regions where they have a natural cavital structure (Figure 1-5), and the trichomes in the partial regions have spiral trichomes as multicellular. The density of long cell trichomes is higher along the veins, particularly on the abaxial surface and at the leaf edges visible to the naked eye. The entire structure was designed by [16], although it seems to be similar with the study they have done, the folding areas caused by rapid drying and excessive dehydration have been seen especially at low magnifications. When 50 nm SiO₂ is applied at low concentration, there is no change in traditional leaf morphology and the classical leaf shape is preserved (Fig 2).

Figure 1. SEM image of control leaf SiO₂NP, density and EDX spectrum.

Figure 2. SEM image of leaf treated with 50-20 (nm-mg/L) SiO₂NP, density and EDX spectrum.

Figure 3. SEM image of leaf treated with 50-50 (nm-mg/L) SiO₂NP, density and EDX spectrum.

Figure 4. SEM image of leaf treated with 100-20 [nm-mg/L] SiO₂NP, density and EDX spectrum.

Figure 5. SEM image of leaf treated with 100-50 [nm-mg /L] SiO₂NP, density and EDX spectrum.

The distribution of trichomes is quite distinct on the leaf surface. When 50-50 nm-ppm sized SiO₂ particles are applied, the results obtained are shown in figure 3. According to these results, it was determined that the leaf surface morphology did not change. The root structure in the SEM images in Figures 7-10 were shown and the cavity cell canals, stem cell morphologies were evaluated. Salt clusters with a maximum size of 1 µm are seen on the control group in SEM images. Root morphology was determined to be normal and in accordance with the literature (Zanao Junior et al. 2014). When the other EDX spectrum and maps were interpreted according to this group, a significant increase was observed in the signals belonging to Si element.

Figure 6. SEM image of control root SiO₂NP, density and EDX spectrum

Figure 7. SEM image of root treated with 50-20 (nm-mg /L) SiO₂NP, density and EDX spectrum.

Figure 8. SEM image of root treated with 50-50 (nm-mg /L) SiO₂NP, density and EDX spectrum.

Figure 9. SEM image of root treated with 100-20 (nm-mg/L) SiO₂NP, density and EDX spectrum.

Figure 10. SEM image of root treated with 100-50 (nm-mg/L) SiO₂NP, density and EDX spectrum.

Elemental maps and EDX spectra for different basic elements of sunflower root and leaf tissues from Figure 1 to 10 are given. Figures 1 and 6 show EDX spectra of control leaf and root surface without SiO₂NP. In this spectrum, elemental maps of Na, Mg, K, Ca, C, O, P, Si, Fe and S were generally taken on the leaf surface. Especially Ca accumulation has been detected on trichomes. No peak of the element Si was detected on the control group. When the other EDX spectra and maps were interpreted depending on the control group, a significant increase was observed in the signals belonging to Na, Si and P elements. In Figure 6, fibrillar root structure is clearly seen and peaks originating from S and Fe elements are seen in the spectrum. EDX spectra of SiO₂NP applied root structures in different sizes and concentrations from Figure 7 to 10 are shown. In these spectra, it was determined that the Si element signal increased due to the increase in SiO₂NP concentration and size, and Si clusters were found in certain regions on the surface.

Discussion

The use of NPs, especially in the agricultural field, has started to attract the attention of politicians and the public in recent years (Rajput et al. 2021, Attia and Elhawati 2021). It has been reported that silicon increases the tolerance capacity of plants against biotic and abiotic stresses such as pests, fungal diseases, salinity and drought and wilting (Alsaedi et al. 2019a). Since there is plenty of Si in the soil, there was no interest in giving Si to the plant at first. Recently, due to increased agricultural activities, it has been reported that the addition of Si is needed to improve plant growth and increase resistance to both biotic and abiotic stresses (El-Ramady et al. 2018). Plants generally absorb silicon in the form of monosilicic and polysilicic acids. Si taken from plant roots first polymerizes and then is transported to stem and leaf tissues and accumulates in these tissues. Si plays a crucial role in various physiological and biochemical stages in plants. For example, Si nanoparticles have been reported to have positive effects such as increasing seed germination and chlorophyll content in *Zea mays* (Yuvakkumar et al. 2011). It has been reported that external application of Si-NP in glycine max plant increases antioxidant activities, K⁺ concentration and

non-enzymatic components, while reducing the negative effects of salt stress by reducing lipid peroxidation, reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation and intracellular Na⁺ concentration (Farhangi-Abriz and Torabian 2018). Advances in nanotechnology have opened new horizons for crop improvement benefits from the use of Si nanoparticles in plants. It has been reported that positive effects on plant growth and development were observed in most of the studies conducted with Si nanoparticles in plants under stress conditions. It has been observed that SiNPs, nano-fertilizers, significantly improve plant growth under many stress conditions (Deshmukh et al. 2017, Bhat et al. 2021). For example, it has been observed that the application of Si increases the resistance to abiotic stress in agricultural products such as rice (Mahdieh et al. 2015), wheat (Tuna et al. 2008) and tomatoes (Almutairi 2016). In our study and similar studies, especially in recent years, nanoparticles have been widely used in different fields to improve human life (Karim and Mohsenzadeh 2012). In some other studies, it has been shown that SiO₂-NPs promote plant growth among various nanoparticle species and improve stress in various plant species (Siddiqui et al. 2014, Yuvakkumar et al. 2011). Although silicon is not necessary for plant growth and development, according to literature data, silicon has been shown to be beneficial for plants, especially under stress conditions. It has been determined that the data obtained from the studies conducted by us are similar to the increase in antioxidant enzyme activities due to the application of SiO₂-NP in previous studies (Hussain et al. 2019, Konate et al. 2018). It has been reported that Si application to plants under salt and drought stress increases SOD, POD, CAT, APX and GR enzymes as well as GSH concentration. In general, based on the results from previous studies, it can be concluded that Si can reduce oxidative damage and regulate antioxidant defense systems in plants. Si has a role in reducing the harmful effects of biotic and abiotic stress in different plants. These beneficial effects can mainly be attributed to the high Si accumulation on the tissue surface, thereby increasing the antioxidant activities of plants and reducing the absorption of soil pollutants such as heavy metals. Si has also been reported to increase salt tolerance, and Si application significantly increases the growth of many plants by concentrating sodium ions in the apoplast and increasing photosynthetic parameters, chlorophyll content and leaf area in salt-treated plants (Farhangi-Abriz and Torabian 2018, Soundararajan et al. 2017). In our study, the accumulation of SiO₂ nanoparticles in root and leaf tissue was demonstrated by scanning electron microscopy, which was also consistent with our finding that there was a general increase in antioxidant enzyme activities. The beneficial effect of Si was previously attributed to a physical barrier that strengthens the cell wall. In this study, the effects of Si on plants have been revealed by reviewing the existing data in the literature and taking into account some criteria. In the light of nanotechnology's interest in agriculture, it can be easily said that the use of silicon nanoparticles is becoming increasingly important.

Conclusions

It is believed that nanotechnology will mark the 21st century as a new industrial and information revolution and will enter all areas of our lives by completing its development by 2025. Nanotechnology is expected to make its weight felt primarily in the field of materials and biotechnology. In addition to the suggested benefits of nanoparticles that rapidly enter our lives in this way, it is necessary to increase the information and studies about their toxicity. In scientific studies on nanoparticles, it is seen that the possible toxic effects of nanoparticles on human and animal health are also investigated. However, studies on plants on this subject are relatively few. However, we can say that studies with plants are also important because plants, which play an important role in the survival of humans and animals, are in direct contact with NPs accumulated in air, water and soil.

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